

The *Songket* Motifs – The Design and Memory of the Malay People

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Abstract

Songket motifs reflect the material artefacts that are embedded with design and memory of the Malay people. *Songket* is a Malay word which means to bring out or to pull a thread from a background cloth or to weave using gold and silver thread. Historically, the Malay textile art of *songket* in Malaysia indicates a symbol of royalty as the rulers. Since the independence from the British in 1957, the Malay, the predominant group in Malaysia, carries through the meaningful symbol of the Malay race forward. The supremacy of this race can be seen reflected in and attached to the *songket* motifs along with the beliefs of animism, Hindu-Buddhism and Islam. The *songket* motifs appear in forms derived from flora, fauna, food, nature and court related objects, a memory passed on through generations via oral traditions. All of these motifs depict the sensitivity towards elements in the daily life of the Malay people as well as life philosophy, adages, phrases and proverbs that become the guidance for the Malay in managing their life. A strong sense of belonging towards the supremacy of this race in Malaysia dignifies the identity and a superior being of the Malay race in Malaysia seen in *songket*. The *songket* motifs highlight the Malay power in a country that is now multi-ethnic, multi-racial, multi religious and multi-lingual. The motifs present an issue of Malaysian identity based on the purity of the Malay race although other foreign influences had played a role in characterizing these people.

Keywords: *Songket*, Malay people, memory, motifs, forms, design, identity, supremacy, sense of belonging

Introduction

This paper explores the design and memory of the Malay people as portrayed in the *songket* motifs. It is significant to note that the *songket* motifs are portrayed in a Malay textile art (Figure 1) called the *songket* found mainly in the states of Kelantan and Terengganu, Malaysia. *Songket* is a Malay word which means to pull a thread from a background cloth or to weave using gold and silver thread (Nawawi, 1989:5). In weaving terms it means to inlay a gold thread or an extra weft (Serian Songket, 1981:3). According to another definition, the *songket* means the act of weaving using the supplementary metallic threads, which are inserted in between, silk or cotton weft or latitudinal threads of the main cloth (Noor, 1993:10).

Figure 1, *Songket*

Methodology

Kelantan and Terengganu became the bases for this paper for the reasons:

1. The only states which still produce the *songket*.
2. Terengganuese and Kelantanese are known for their practice of and strong beliefs in traditional Malay customs and teachings.
3. These two states illustrate the most traditional settings and the least affected by foreign influences.

In oral cultures such as the Malay culture, oral communication is dominant and takes precedence in any activities involving acquiring information. It is known as a way for the Malay people to express their sensitivities in a specific design through their memory. The oral culture allows the Malay people to express their emotion through their design in the *songket* motifs. Custom allows such activity to become the most important method of gaining knowledge, again based on respect to the elders and the wiser ones. Moreover, the oral tradition expresses a very strong cultural value and in the *songket* motifs adages, metaphors, proverbs and philosophies are distinctive. Thus, the undertaken methodology is concerned with the design and memory manifestation of the Malay culture.

An in-depth interview is much more suitable for interactions in the Malay culture for exploration purposes. The elders and the *songket* weavers are interviewed due to their vast knowledge and memory of the *songket* productions. Information includes ideas and

philosophies embedded in the *songket* motifs and cannot be found in any written texts or manuscripts. The Malay culture teaches its people to respect the elders, for they are more knowledgeable and wiser and the younger generations must learn to respect the elders for the knowledge they carry. An old saying expresses that who tastes the salt first is the most informed person referring to the elders' greater experience and knowledge (Clifford, 1913: 103). Thus, a Malay person is advised to seek knowledge not from books alone but to seek with the assistance of teachers. In this traditional custom, the Malay culture itself tells an enormous amount about the identity and memory of the people as seen in their traditions, customs and behaviours. The interviews were conducted simultaneously with the collection of the visual evidence to support the information collected. Slides and photographs are logical fiction. Moreover, they are designed merely to capture what is distinctive in *the photographic relation and the photographer's interest* (Scruton, 1983:103). Thus, the photographs and slides are vital because they document non-verbal behaviour and communication, representations of Malay memory in design.

History of *songket*

Historically, the *songket* threads were of gold, with the application of silver threads beginning after the influx of Indian and Arab traders to the Malay Peninsula in the 13th to 16th centuries. The *songket* weaving flourished during the Malacca Malay Sultanate Empire when trade to the Malay Peninsula was at its peak during the 15th century. The port city of Malacca, the administrative and economic centre of the empire drew traders from India, China, the Arab world and the West via India. Hence came the materials necessary for the *songket* weaving (Serian Songket, 1981:4). Malay historical texts indicated that the *songket* costumes could only be worn by the royalty, the court officials elected by the sultans, and those who received awards. There were very strict rules of attire and for the wearing of the *songket* costumes as written in traditional law texts of The Canon Law of Malacca and The Littoral Laws of Malacca. Those who failed to comply could be punished severely. It can be posited that the *songket* motifs represent the identity and ethnicity namely in the Malay traditional political, economic and social systems, which was passed on through generations via memory and oral traditions.

***Songket* motifs design and memory**

Spatial harmony, balance, rhythm, repetition, and sizes of the motifs express a high level of

artistic achievement. According to Su (1997), a wood carver of Terengganu, the arrangement of motifs in Malay art pieces always deals with *the appreciation of the Malay people of God's creation. The way to appreciate God's (Allah) creation is by looking at and into nature to find answers to human existence.* However, before the Malay people were converted to Islam after the 12th century, the Malay people were animists, Buddhists and Hindus (Kasimin, 1991:xi). They were producing art long before the conversion to Islam. However, the philosophy in these religions is in keeping with Malay devotion to the divine power of the Supreme Being. The meaning of motifs, spaces and gaps between motifs are designed according to these religious beliefs. It could be suggested that the *songket* motifs of the past represented the animist belief and the assimilation with Hindu-Buddhist and Islamic ideologies. They were the memory of the Malay people.

As the Malay people always believe in the united we stand, divided we fall, the arrangement of motifs also is influenced by the same concept. The motifs always appear in numbers to signify unity of the community creating the patterns. The *songket* motifs are divided into several categories. They are motifs derived from flora and fauna that have been stylised because of Islamic religious restrictions, foods, nature and significant court objects. In order to comprehend the symbolism that exists in the motifs, the location of the motifs or structure in *songket* has to be considered. The hierarchy of locations in the structure are the head followed by body and foot and supporting for the head (Figure 2).

Figure 2, structure of *songket*

The head plays the role of carrying the hidden meaning behind the portrayed motifs. The motifs occupying the body area act as supporting motifs combined in various patterns. The

foot is filled with solid and stable design, and *kendik* (supporting the head) is filled with thin and ornate design (Serian Songket, 1981:8).

Malaysia's tropical location provides an abundance of plants. The Malay people have exploited the medicinal properties of these plants. They have successfully used all parts of plants: the flowers, roots, leaves, fruits, bark and even seeds. Plants are portrayed repeatedly in Malay art because they are believed to have the power of healing those who own the art pieces. However, according to Coatalen (1982:110), *plants are not an Islamic symbol and further the extremely widespread floral motifs can be explained by the intrinsic beauty of the flowers. Plants are extremely well represented in Malaysia. Malays use plants on a variety of occasions, as food, medicine, drugs, offering and decoration. To know the meaning of the plants one has to identify them, which is not easy, for botany is not an easy knowledge to acquire.* The most significant plant used and illustrated is the motif of bamboo shoot. The importance of bamboo to the Malay people is mentioned numerous times in the Malay proverbs, where the growth of the bamboo is identified with human development. Therefore, the growing stages of this plant are meant to be an example in educating and bringing children into adulthood.

According to Jusoh (1997) of Terengganu, the bamboo shoot motif was located within folklore long before the coming of Islam. When the Malays converted to Islam, the symbolic meaning of the bamboo shoot was changed to be incorporated with Islamic teachings leading away from the superstitious and supernatural beliefs. However, the folkloristic beliefs regarding bamboo shoot motifs still remain deeply embedded in the Malay culture. This is because most of *Malay historical texts combined facts with myths, legends and folkloristic belief* (Osman, 1988:130). The long period of Hindu-Buddhist influences had deepened the beliefs in spiritual elements and supernatural beings, which existed in the early Malay communities of the archipelago (Ibid). Mohamed (1997), a Malay Kelantanese historian and religious teacher (Sufism), believes that *one should look into his/her religion to obtain a deeper comprehension of the meaning in his/her art.* Diagrammatically, the bamboo shoot (Figure 3) motif is represented in a triangular shape, in the head pointing at each other.

Figure 3, bamboo shoot motif

The bamboo shoot represents the universe. The motifs in bamboo shoot express *the beauty of the universe as they are derived from 'something beautiful' (referring to the Divine Essence of God)* (Ibid). The 'universe' is depicted in a four division triangle (Figure 4) (Ibid).

Figure 4, bamboo shoot symbolism

1. *Alam Syhadah* (universe) - signifies the reality or physicality of the world/universe.
2. *Alam Mithal* (unseen world) - designates the unseen and less understood world/universe.
3. *Alam Arwah* (spiritual world) - the degree of understanding of human kind towards this world as basically minimal.
4. At the apex and confined to a small dot is the *Zat Allah* (Divine Essence) and the place for Divine Power and Supreme Being (Mohamed, 1984:31).

Spices are other sources for motifs. Cloves and star anise, renowned for their fragrance, are principal motifs supporting the bamboo shoot. Jusoh (1997) pointed out that cloves and star anise possess some medicinal values. Apart from relieving tooth-aches and bad breath, both spices help to heal wounds after child birth and to ease post-natal distress (Zakaria and Mohd, 1993:11) and cloves can be used as moth balls to preserve delicate costumes from pests while releasing sweet fragrance (Aziz, 1997). Clove (Figure 5) and star anise (Figure 6) motifs appear in small representation. They exist as principal supporting motifs to balance the composition of the pattern. According to Jusoh (1997), the motifs of cloves and star anise are the ‘invisible’ boundary defining the outline of bigger motifs.

Figure 5, clove motif

Figure 6, star anise motif

Most of the flowers that are portrayed in the *songket* motifs have sweet fragrance, are small to medium in size, white and cream in colour and possess some medicinal properties. Traditionally, the flowers were believed to have special effect in revitalising and rejuvenating the bather when used in scented bath. Nature in the Malay society has always been a reflection of the creation of the Supreme Being. A flower connected to a stem symbolises the strength of a thread to the teaching of Islam (Figure 7). Loss of faith in Allah, the Supreme Being, destroys the belief of the people in their faith, causing them go astray (Jusoh, 1997).

Figure 7, diagram of a flower

Teratai (lotus), according to Mohamed (1984:35), is the ‘mother’ of all flowers as far as the people of the Southeast Asia is concerned. Interpretation of lotus (Figure 8) indicates various very strong religious beliefs bringing about traditions and customs.

Figure 8, eight petalled lotus

The interpretation has changed in the process of appropriating but the shape of the motif remained the same. Yin, a *songket* weaver and producer of Kelantan, described the lotus motifs appear in four petalled-lotus and eight petalled-lotus (Yin and various *songket* weavers, 1997, 2003 and 2004). Mohamed (1984:36) says that the petals of the lotus symbolise levels of being, as the lotus has always been associated with the Malay culture and religions. The lotus is also known as the twelve petalled sun and the six petalled sun (Ibid). When transformed into motifs, the lotus comes in different shapes of four, six, eight and twelve petalled lotus.

Diagrammatically, the circle that holds the lotus petals together according to Mohamed represents the *kalbu/kalbun* (‘trueself’) (Figure 9). This representation holds the functions of the body. The *kalbu/kalbun* (‘trueself’) is situated in the heart of a human and can only be reached or touched through *rasa* (feelings) (Ibid).

The feelings and the other eight parts of the body in total made up nine parts of the human body where *the rasa (feelings) is connected to the stem of the plant. In humankind, the rasa (feelings) is connected to the power of the Divine Being through his devotion in a spiritual relationship* (Ibid). The eight petalled lotus symbolises the parts of the human body. The functions are reflected as follows, describing the human body parts have to work together in order to give their fullest devotion to the Divine Being (Ibid).

1. Forehead	2. Chest
3. Right shoulder	4. Left shoulder
5. Right elbow	6. Left elbow
7. Right leg	8. Left leg

Figure 9, the human body parts in relation to eight petalled lotus

The four petalled lotus signifies the four elements of *earth, water, fire and wind* (Figure 10) in relation to the human character (Ahmad, 1982:12).

1. the earth element - associated with coldness and dryness.
2. the water element - associated with coldness and wetness.
3. the fire element – associated with hotness and dryness.
4. the air element - associated with hotness and wetness.

These characters must co-exist in balance and harmony in the human body. Lack of an element will result in an imbalanced body, causing sickness. Traditional medicine practitioners believe that using natural sources such as flowers for medicine will apparently heal the sickness through the process of rejuvenating and revitalising, thus bringing balance to the human body.

Figure 10, four-petalled lotus and elements in human body

The commonly used fruit motifs are based on the mangosteen (Figure 11) and Malay gooseberry (Figure 12). The character of a mangosteen is expressed in an old Malay adage of black is the shell, but sweetness lies inside on the judging of a person's personality.

Figure 11, mangosteen

Figure 12, Malay gooseberry

It is reflected in the contrast of colours between the black shell of the fruit and the white fleshy pulp. The mangosteen also symbolises the reflection of one's feelings or one's inner self as related to human spiritual state (Dawa, 1997). It also signifies purity of heart in one's relationship with the Supreme Being. Malay gooseberry is particularly intriguing because of its size. It is a small yellow acidic fruit with a very sour taste. It has a strength that is metaphorically similar to the Western adage *don't judge the book by its cover*. Therefore, this metaphor has always been used to characterise the social behaviour of the Malay people.

The coming of Islam and the spread of Islamic teachings from 8th century AD onward saw the diminishing representation of animals in Malay art. Orthodox Islamic beliefs written in the Al-Hadis forbid animals' representation in any art form, stated *on the day of Judgement when the painter (any artist) stands before the Throne of God, he will be commanded to put life into the works of art he has created and when he confesses his inability to do so, he will be forthwith cast down into Hell* (Arnold, 1932:153). However, the belief did not prevent the Malays from recreating images of animals in the *songket* motifs. According to Hussein (1997), a wood carver and a dagger maker of Kelantan, the animals that are portrayed frequently in Malay arts are the motifs of the cockerel's tail and sea horses. These motifs are stylised and turned into geometrical patterns aligned with the teachings of Islam. The abstract forms of the sea horses (Figure 13), cockerel's tails, butterfly etc. capture the beauty of these creatures. Both animals possess intricate appearances and are admired for strength and perseverance symbolising the spiritual belief and powerful Malay warriors.

Figure 13, seahorse

The cockerel's spur motifs were portrayed for their colourful appearance and the strength of the cocks. The cockerel's spur is also a small weapon used by the Malay warriors. The weapon symbolises the artistry of weaponry design and concealed strength in a small-sized dagger (Terengganu State Museum, 1997, 2003 and 2004). The shape of sea horses motif was derived from the intricate form of the sea horses and associated with the fishermen and sailors in their seafaring journeys. The creature possesses some medicinal properties. The Malay people also believe that sea horses have the ability to ward off evil spells; thus, dried sea horses are hung on the door for such task (Hussein, 1997).

The awareness of the beautiful creation of God is reflected in the portrayal of elements of nature. Mountains, waves (Figure 14), rain, clouds, water are examples of natural elements

that are captured in the motifs.

Figure 14, waves

Motifs derived from nature started long before the coming of foreign influences to the Malay Archipelago. Malay animism that held that spirits lived in every living thing ensured that the elements were illustrated in all the functional arts. However, the motif of mountains (Figure 15) stressed a very strong Buddhist influence.

Figure 15, mountains

The Buddhist religious teachings enforced the strong animist belief that magical and spiritual powers existed in elements in nature. Thus, the elements from nature became the symbols and sources for creation in art forms (Ismail, 1994:25). According to the teaching of Buddhism, the mountain links the worlds, *servng as a channel of communication between the realms of existence. The tip of the mountain is the focal point for such interchange* (Snodgrass, 1985:260). Such faith remained in the Malay society for a long time transcending different periods of foreign influence. The faith was strengthened by the Hindu myth that *the chariots of the gods, the sky travellers, alight upon the summit of the World Mountain* (Ibid). This was believed to be the point of contact between man and gods. *The summit of the cosmic mountain is not only the highest point of the earth; it is also the earth's navel, the point at which the creation began* (Eliade, 1964:261).

The Islamic belief expresses that the tip of the mountain is an abstract location where one can find God but only through looking into nature and understanding it. The concept of communicating with God through the tip of the mountain is also applied in the architecture of the mosques. Physically, a dome that points upward serves the same function as applied in Buddhist temple (Yatim, 1989:42). Diagrammatically, the mountains motifs can be found mostly at the foot of the *songket* structure, stating its stability and boldness (Figure 16).

Figure 16, mountain in Islamic belief

Billowing clouds motif illustrates strength and stability despite its soft appearance. Water canal represents the agrarian economy of the Malay people, where the canal is used to irrigate the plantations. The function of water canal of watering plants itself is associated with the people's unity through the act of helping each other. The motifs taken from nature symbolise the notion of growth, spiritually and physically. They allow the process of nurturing life and seeking perfection. The nature represents the vehicle for humankind to use in trying to understand what faith and religion will offer in achieving the 'higher' level of spiritual beings. However, the beliefs of the Malay people interacted with several religious beliefs before coming to Islamic belief. Myths and superstitious beliefs starting in the animist and Hindu-Buddhist periods became intertwined with the Islamic religious beliefs. Therefore, it is this blend that characterises the Malay people. These assimilations

are visible in the rituals and ceremonies in contemporary Malaysia. However, the fundamental religious belief is strictly Islam.

Foods become part of the *songket* motifs for their moulded shapes and ingredients required to produce them. Most of the foods portrayed in the motifs require a mixture of brown sugar, coconut milk and flour as contained in honey sweet cake and glutinous rice sweet cake (Figures 17 & 18).

Figure 17, honey sweet cake

Figure 18, glutinous rice sweet cake

Dawa (1997), a researcher in traditional Malay motifs, stressed that to understand the importance of the foods is to analyse the ingredients. *Any single ingredient is tasteless without the other*. A lot of combined effort is needed to prepare the foods, thus making them the food of a community. The bonding of the ingredients symbolises unity in a community where the individualistic act is least recognised. The feeling is consistent with the old Malay saying translated as *the load is equally shared regardless of the weight*. The foods represent the participation of a community and preserve unity and the repetition and combination of motifs indicate the idea of the strength of communal activities.

Chess was a favourite game for royalty. The pattern of the chess board (Figure 19) is woven onto motifs to create the chess board pattern. Court's fences (Figure 20) motif is located mainly at the foot of the structure, indicating a function similar to the mountain motif. It provides a visual stability and boldness filled with ornate design. It also provides a boundary or a frame to the whole composition.

Figure 19, chess board

Figure 20, court's fence

Conclusion

The *songket* motifs via oral traditions depict the traditional establishment of the Malay political system (associating spirituality with Divine Kingship), largely agrarian economy and social system expressing communal activities. These motifs also indicate the process of reshaping cultural values through assimilation with the Hindu-Buddhist and ultimately Islamic cultural influences combined with the animist traditions. The flexibility of accommodating foreign ideologies in the *songket* motifs agrees with the concept of cohesiveness of *a form of art to combine and to oppose to become a system of multiple references* (Firth, 1975:42). The motifs also signify that the Malay culture today is a product of assimilation that already allowed the process of assimilation and transformation of cultural identity. However, cultural identity in the *songket* motifs will remain culturally Malay as *'the cultural change involves modified social patterns, but not all social change produces cultural change'* (Davis, 1970:22). However, the concepts of 'growth', 'sense of unity' and 'human spirituality' will remain a part of the Malay cultural identity embedded with Islamic teaching portrayed in the *songket* motifs. The traditions of expressing memory and design in *songket* motifs live on.

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